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FOR MATHEMATICAL FORMALIZATION OF DIFFERENTIAL POSITIONAL GAME

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FOR MATHEMATICAL FORMALIZATION OF DIFFERENTIAL POSITIONAL GAME.

Zhukovskiy V. I., Zhukovskaya L. V., Smirnova L. V.

Abstract. The academician Andrey Izmailovich Subbotin proposed in 1988 the counterexample for used in that time mathematical formalization of positional differential game: it turned out that during the time of duration of the game new motions can appear which could not be taken into account in initial position. Namely the present article is devoted to these problems.

Keywords: *differential game, noncooperative game, step-by-step motion, quasimotion, terminal payoff functions*

Mathematics as an expression of the human mind reflects the active will,
the contemplative reason, and the desire for aesthetic perfection.

Its basic elements are logic and intuition, analysis and construction,
generality and individuality. Though different traditions may emphasize
different aspects, it is only the interplay of these antithetic forces
and the struggle for their synthesis that constitute the life, usefulness,
and supreme value of mathematical science.

— Courant¹

¹Richard Courant, (1888–1972), was a German-born American mathematician, educator and scientific organizer who made significant advances in the calculus of variations. A quote from *The Australian Mathematics Teacher*, vols. 39–40, Australian Association of Mathematics Teachers, 1983, p. 3.

1. NONCOOPERATIVE POSITIONAL DIFFERENTIAL GAME OF N PLAYERS

The mathematical model of a noncooperative positional differential game of N players (NPDG) is an ordered quadruple

$$\langle \mathbb{N}, \Sigma, \{\mathfrak{U}_i\}_{i \in \mathbb{N}}, \{\mathcal{J}_i\}_{i \in \mathbb{N}} \rangle, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbb{N} = \{1, \dots, N\}$ denotes the set of players; Σ is a controlled dynamic system whose state $x(t)$ evolves over time t in accordance with the vector ordinary differential equation

$$\dot{x} = f(t, x, u_1, \dots, u_N), \quad x(t_0) = x_0; \quad (2)$$

\mathfrak{U}_i gives the set of all strategies (actions) U_i of player $i \in \mathbb{N}$; \mathcal{J}_i is the payoff function of player i , and its value (called payoff) is adopted for assessing the performance of player i .

2. CONTROLLED SYSTEM

The state $x(t)$ of this game (conflict) at a current time instant t satisfies the vector ordinary differential equation (2), where $x \in \mathbb{R}^m$ (i. e., the state vector belongs to the m -dimensional real Euclidean space composed of all ordered collections of m real values in the form of columns, with the standard scalar product and Euclidean norm $\|\cdot\|$); the time t varies from $t_0 \geq 0$ до $\vartheta > t_0$, and a current position is $(t, x) \in [t_0, \vartheta] \times \mathbb{R}^m$; the control of player i is $u_i \in Q_i \subset \mathbb{R}^{n_i}$ ($i \in \mathbb{N}$). Now, we introduce the following assumptions.

Conditions 1. *The components of the m -dimensional vector function $f(t, x, u_1, \dots, u_N)$ are continuous in all variables. The sets Q_i ($i \in \mathbb{N}$) are closed and bounded; i. e.; $Q_i \in \text{comp } \mathbb{R}^{n_i}$, and*

$$u = (u_1, \dots, u_N) \in Q = \prod_{i \in \mathbb{N}} Q_i \subset \mathbb{R}^n \quad (n = \sum_{i \in \mathbb{N}} n_i).$$

For each bounded domain G in the space of positions (t, x) , there exists a specific Lipschitz constant $\lambda(G)$ such that

$$\|f(t^{(1)}, x^{(1)}, u) - f(t^{(2)}, x^{(2)}, u)\| \leq \lambda(G)(\|x^{(1)} - x^{(2)}\| + |t^{(1)} - t^{(2)}|)$$

for all $(t^{(j)}, x^{(j)}) \in G$ ($j = 1, 2$), uniformly in $u \in Q$.

There exists a $\gamma = \text{const} > 0$ such that, for all $t \in [t_0, \vartheta]$ and $u \in Q$, the sublinear growth conditions hold:

$$\|f(t, x, u)\| \leq \gamma(1 + \|x\|). \quad (3)$$

Note that Conditions 1 guarantee the existence of unique and continuable solutions $x(\cdot) = \{x(t), t_0 \leq t \leq \vartheta\}$ of the system (2) on an interval $[t_0, \vartheta]$ for all $x(t_0) = x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^m$ and any Borel measurable n -dimensional vector functions $u(t) \in Q \forall t \in [t_0, \vartheta]$.

3. STRATEGIES AND STRATEGY PROFILES

The need for a well-timed response to all possible disturbances of a controlled system leads to the principle of feedback control. For the system (2), this principle can be implemented using the mathematical formalization of players' controls (strategies) in noncooperative differential games suggested by Krasovskii and his followers [3–5]. Let us formulate several concepts required for further presentation: a strategy of player i , a strategy profile, and the motions of the system (2) that are induced by them.

Definition 1. A strategy U_i of player i in the NPDG (1) is a function $u_i(t, x)$ whose values satisfy the inclusion

$$u_i(t, x) \subseteq Q_i, \quad (4)$$

at each possible position (t, x) , where Q_i is a given compact subset of the n_i -dimensional Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^{n_i} .

The function $u_i(t, x)$ in (4) can be multi-valued, particularly, $u_i(t, x) = Q_i$. A correspondence between a strategy U_i and a function $u_i(t, x)$ will be denoted by $U_i \div u_i(t, x)$ and the set of all strategies of player i by \mathfrak{A}_i . A complete collection of strategies $U = (U_1, \dots, U_N) \in \mathfrak{A} = \prod_{i \in \mathbb{N}} \mathfrak{A}_i$ will be called a strategy profile of the game (1).

Player i chooses a control u_i . Now, consider the concept of a quasimotion of the system (2) from an initial position $(t_0, x_0) \in [0, \vartheta) \times \mathbb{R}^m$ that is induced by a fixed strategy U_i of player i ($i \in \mathbb{N}$). The theoretical results presented below were established in [1]. Note that the original concept of a motion of a controlled system (see [3–5]) has been modified in view of the two counterexamples suggested by Subbotin and Kononenko [1, p. 16]. The first example demonstrated a possible occurrence of new motions that were absent in an original pencil of motions; the second example, a possible loss of some motions from that pencil. These negative effects can be avoided using the mathematical formalization of a quasimotion developed by Zhukovskiy in [1]; see that paper for a detailed proof of the facts listed in section 4 below.

4. PIECEWISE CONTINUOUS STEP-BY-STEP QUASIMOTIONS

We will introduce step-by-step quasimotions differing from their counterparts [4, p. 8] by the following properties: *they are piecewise continuous and may have discontinuities of the first kind (finite jumps) at any partition points.*

Step-by-step quasimotions. We define the step-by-step quasimotions (piecewise continuous step-by-step motions) induced by a strategy $U_i \in \mathfrak{A}_i$ and a strategy profile $U = (U_1, \dots, U_N) \in \mathfrak{A}$. Without special mention, let the system (2) satisfy Conditions 1.

Consider an initial position $(t_0, x_0) \in [0, \vartheta] \times \mathbb{R}^m$, a value $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ and a chosen strategy $U_i \div u_i(t, x)$, $U_i \in \mathfrak{A}_i$. We cover the interval $[t_0, \vartheta]$ by a system Δ of half-intervals $\tau_j \leq t < \tau_{j+1}$ ($j = 0, 1, \dots, r(\Delta) - 1$), where $\tau_0 \geq t_0$ and $\tau_{r(\Delta)} = \vartheta$. Next, let $u_{\mathbb{N} \setminus \{i\}}(t) = (u_1(t), \dots, u_{i-1}(t), u_{i+1}(t), \dots, u_N(t))$ be Borel measurable vector functions such that, for all $t \in [t_0, \vartheta]$,

$$u_{\mathbb{N} \setminus \{i\}}(t) \in Q_{\mathbb{N} \setminus \{i\}} = \prod_{j \in \mathbb{N}, j \neq i} Q_j.$$

A step-by-step quasimotion of the system (2) from an initial position $(t_0, x_0) \in [0, \vartheta] \times \mathbb{R}^m$ that is induced by

- a) a strategy $U_i \div u_i(t, x) \subseteq Q_i$,
- b) a partition $\Delta : t_0 \leq \tau_0 < \tau_1 < \dots < \tau_{r(\Delta)} = \vartheta$,
and
- c) a value $\alpha \in [0, 1]$,

is any function

$$x(\cdot, U_i, \Delta, \alpha) = \{x(t, \tau_0, x_0, \hat{x}_0, u_{\mathbb{N} \setminus \{i\}}(\cdot), U_i, \Delta, \alpha), \tau_0 \leq t \leq \vartheta\}$$

that satisfies the quasi step-by-step equation

$$x(t, U_i, \Delta, \alpha) = \hat{x}_i + \int_{\tau_j}^t f(\tau, x(\tau, U_i, \Delta, \alpha), u_{\mathbb{N} \setminus \{i\}}(\tau), u_i(\tau_j, x_j)) d\tau \quad (5)$$

where $\tau_j \leq t < \tau_{j+1}$ ($j = 0, 1, \dots, r(\Delta) - 1$), subject to the constraint

$$\sum_{j=0}^{r(\Delta)-1} \|\hat{x}_j - x_0(\tau_j, U_i, \Delta, \alpha)\| \leq \alpha, \quad (6)$$

where $x_0(\tau_j, U_i, \Delta, \alpha)$ denotes the value at the time instant $t = \tau_j$ of the solution $x(t, U_i, \Delta, \alpha)$ of equation (5) extended to the right on the interval $\tau_{j-1} \leq t < \tau_j$ ($j = 1, 2, \dots, r(\Delta) - 1$), i. e.,

$$x_0(\tau_j, U_i, \Delta, \alpha) = \hat{x}_{j-1} + \int_{\tau_{j-1}}^{\tau_j} f(\tau, x(\tau, U_i, \Delta, \alpha), u_{\mathbb{N} \setminus \{i\}}(\tau), u_i(\tau_{j-1}, \hat{x}_{j-1})) d\tau \quad (7)$$

$$x(\tau_0, U_i, \Delta, \alpha) = \hat{x}_0, \quad x_0(t_0, U_i, \Delta, \alpha) = x_0.$$

Unlike the step-by-step motions considered in [4, p. 33], the step-by-step quasimotions may have finite jumps $\|\hat{x}_j - x_0(\tau_j, U_i, \Delta, \alpha)\| \neq 0$ at partition points τ_j . The sum of these jumps must not exceed a given value α ; see Figure 1. This fact will be indicated

Fig. 1. Step-by-step motions and step-by-step quasimotions

by a proper notation $x(t, U_i, \Delta, \alpha)$ for quasimotions, which includes α among other variables. For $\alpha = 0$, a step-by-step quasimotion turns into a common step-by-step motion from [4, p. 33].

Denote by $\mathcal{X}(t_0, x_0, U_i)$ the set of all such step-by-step quasimotions of the system (2) from an initial position (t_0, x_0) that are induced by a fixed strategy U_i , all possible partitions Δ , all values $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ and any Borel measurable functions $u_{\mathbb{N} \setminus \{i\}}(t) \in Q_{\mathbb{N} \setminus \{i\}} = \prod_{s \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{i\}} Q_s$.

Consider equations (5) and (7) with $\tau_j \leq t < \tau_{j+1}$ ($j = 0, 1, \dots, r(\Delta) - 1$) and let $u_{\mathbb{N} \setminus \{i\}}(\tau) = u_{\mathbb{N} \setminus \{i\}}(\tau_j, \hat{x}_j)$. Then these equations define a step-by-step quasimotion $x(\cdot, \tau_0, x_0, \hat{x}_0, U, \Delta, \alpha)$ of the system (2) from an initial position (t_0, x_0) that is induced by a strategy profile $U = (U_1, \dots, U_N) \in \mathfrak{A}$, where $U = (U_1, \dots, U_i, \dots, U_N)$ is a given strategy profile from \mathfrak{A} .

Hereinafter, $M_m[t_0, \vartheta]$ will stand for the set of all bounded m -dimensional vector functions $z(t)$, $t \in [t_0, \vartheta]$ with the norm

$$\|z(\cdot)\|_{M_m[t_0, \vartheta]} = \sup_{t_0 \leq t \leq \vartheta} \|z(t)\|.$$

Proposition 1. The set $\mathcal{X}(t_0, x_0, U_i)$ of all step-by-step quasimotions $x(\cdot, U_i, \Delta, \alpha)$ of the system (2) from an initial position (t_0, x_0) that are induced by a fixed strategy U_i , all possible partitions Δ , any values $\alpha \in [0, 1]$, and any Borel measurable functions

$u_{\mathbb{N}\setminus\{i\}}(t) \in Q_{\mathbb{N}\setminus\{i\}}$ is bounded by norm in the space $M_m[t_0, \vartheta]$. In other words, there exists $k = \text{const} > 0$ such that, for all $x(\cdot, U_i, \Delta, \alpha)$,

$$\|x(\cdot, U_i, \Delta, \alpha)\|_{M_m[t_0, \vartheta]} \leq k.$$

In a similar way, the set $\mathcal{X}(t_0, x_0, U)$ of all step-by-step quasimotions $x(\cdot, U, \Delta, \alpha)$ of the system (2) from an initial position (t_0, x_0) that are induced by a fixed strategy profile $U \in \mathfrak{A}$, all possible partitions Δ , and any values $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ is bounded by norm in the space $M_m[t_0, \vartheta]$.

Quasimotions and their properties. Now, we will define quasimotions as the continuous limits (in the space $M_m[t_0, \vartheta]$) of different sequences of step-by-step quasimotions constructed above.

Definition 2. A quasimotion $x[\cdot] = \{x[t, t_0, x_0, U_i], t_0 \leq t \leq \vartheta\}$ of the system (2) from an initial position (t_0, x_0) that is induced by a strategy $U_i \in \mathfrak{A}_i$ is any continuous function $x[\cdot] = \{x[t], t_0 \leq t \leq \vartheta\}$, on the interval $[t_0, \vartheta]$ representing in the metric of the space $M_m[t_0, \vartheta]$ the limit of some converging sequence of step-by-step quasimotions (extended to the left to t_0 if $\tau_0^{(r)} > t_0$) as $r \rightarrow \infty$ and $m \rightarrow \infty$, i.e.,

$$x(\cdot, U_i, \Delta^{(r)}, \alpha^{(m)}) = \{x(t, \tau_0^{(r)}, x_0, x_0^{(r)}, u_{\mathbb{N}\setminus\{i\}}^{(r)}(\cdot), \Delta^{(r)}, \alpha^{(m)}), t_0 \leq t \leq \vartheta\},$$

where

$$\text{diam } \Delta^{(r)} \rightarrow 0,$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} |\tau_0^{(r)} - t_0| + \|x_0^{(r)} - x_0\| &\rightarrow 0 \text{ as } r \rightarrow \infty, \\ \alpha^{(m)} &\rightarrow 0 \text{ as } m \rightarrow \infty; \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

here

$$\begin{aligned} \text{diam } \Delta^{(r)} &= \max_j \left[\tau_{j+1}^{(r)} - \tau_j^{(r)} \right], \\ 0 &\leq \alpha^{(m)} \leq 1 \quad (r, m = 1, 2, \dots). \end{aligned}$$

Thus, under (2) this sequence $\{x(\cdot, U_i, \Delta^{(r)}, \alpha^{(m)})\}$ satisfies the condition

$$\sup_{t_0 \leq t \leq \vartheta} \|x[t] - x(t, U_i, \Delta^{(r)}, \alpha^{(m)})\| \rightarrow 0.$$

Denote by $\mathcal{X}[t_0, x_0, U_i]$ the pencil of the constructed quasimotions of the system (2). Different quasimotions of this pencil are implemented with different sequences $\Delta^{(r)}$, $\alpha^{(m)}$ and different $u_{\mathbb{N}\setminus\{i\}}^{(r)}(t) \in Q_{\mathbb{N}\setminus\{i\}}$ that can be used to construct the step-by-step quasimotions converging to the quasimotions $x[\cdot, t_0, x_0, U_i]$.

The quasimotions $x[\cdot, t_0, x_0, U]$ of the system (2) from an initial position (t_0, x_0) that are induced by a strategy profile $U \in \mathfrak{A}$ are defined by analogy. The pencil of such quasimotions will be denoted by $\mathcal{X}[t_0, x_0, U]$.

Consider the properties of these pencils of quasimotions.

Proposition 2. A pencil $\mathcal{X}[t_0, x_0, U_i]$ is a non-empty, bounded by norm and closed subset in the space $C_m[t_0, \vartheta] \subset M_m[t_0, \vartheta]$. The same properties hold for the pencil $\mathcal{X}[t_0, x_0, U]$.

Proposition 3. For any initial position $(t_0, x_0) \in [0, \vartheta] \times \mathbb{R}^m$ any strategy U_i and any strategy profile $U \in \mathfrak{A}$ the cutsets of the corresponding pencils of quasimotions by the hyperplane $t = \vartheta$,

$$X[\vartheta, t_0, x_0, U_i] = \mathcal{X}[t_0, x_0, U_i] \cap \{t = \vartheta\},$$

and

$$X[\vartheta, t_0, x_0, U] = \mathcal{X}[t_0, x_0, U] \cap \{t = \vartheta\},$$

are non-empty compact sets in \mathbb{R}^m .

Proposition 4. Whatever the initial position $(t_0, x_0) \in [0, \vartheta] \times \mathbb{R}^m$ and strategy profile $U = (U_1, \dots, U_i, \dots, U_N) \in \mathfrak{A}$ are each quasimotion $x[\cdot, t_0, x_0, U]$ from the pencil $\mathcal{X}[t_0, x_0, U]$ is contained in the pencil $\mathcal{X}[t_0, x_0, U_i]$ ($i \in \mathbb{N}$), i. e.,

$$\mathcal{X}[t_0, x_0, U] \subset \mathcal{X}[t_0, x_0, U_i] \quad (i \in \mathbb{N}),$$

and hence

$$X[\vartheta, t_0, x_0, U \div Q] \subset X[\vartheta, t_0, x_0, U_i \div Q_i] \quad (i \in \mathbb{N}).$$

In what follows, also we will use the attainability domain of the system (2) from an initial position (t_0, x_0) , i. e.,

$$X[\vartheta] = X[\vartheta, t_0, x_0, U \div Q] = X[U \div Q] = \bigcup_{U \in \mathfrak{A}} x[\vartheta, t_0, x_0, U].$$

Remark 1. By Definitions 1 and 2 (strategies, strategy profiles, and the quasimotions of the system (2) from an initial position (t_0, x_0) induced by them),

a) for the strategy $U_i \div Q_i$ of player i , the pencil of quasimotions is

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{X}[t_0, x_0, U_i \div Q_i] &= \{x[t, t_0, x_0, U_i], t \in [t_0, \vartheta] \mid \forall U_i \in \mathfrak{A}_i\} = \\ &= \bigcup_{U_i \in \mathfrak{A}_i} \{x[t, t_0, x_0, U_i], t_0 \leq t \leq \vartheta\}; \end{aligned}$$

b) for a strategy profile $U \div Q$, the pencil of quasimotions is

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{X}[t_0, x_0, U \div Q] &= \{x[t, t_0, x_0, U], t_0 \leq t \leq \vartheta \mid \forall U \in \mathfrak{A}\} = \\ &= \bigcup_{U \in \mathfrak{A}} \{x[t, t_0, x_0, U], t_0 \leq t \leq \vartheta\}. \end{aligned}$$

Completeness of pencil of quasimotions. The following result justifies the transition from the motions of the system (2) in Krasovskii's sense to the quasimotions.

Theorem 1. *For any position $(t^*, x[t^*])$, where $t^* \in [t_0, \vartheta]$ u $x[\cdot]$ is some quasimotion from the pencil $\mathcal{X}[t_0, x_0, U]$*

$$X[\vartheta, t^*, x[t^*], U] \subset X[\vartheta, t_0, x_0, U] \quad \forall U \in \mathfrak{A}.$$

Thus, in any quasimotion induced by a given strategy profile U from a given initial position, there may not occur or disappear segments of any other quasimotions absent in the original pencil that are induced by the same strategy profile from the same initial position. For the quasimotions formalized in [4], such segments of motions may appear; see below the counterexamples by Kononenko and Subbotin.

The next statement is similar to Theorem 1.

Proposition 5. *For any position $(t^*, x[t^*])$, where $t^* \in [t_0, \vartheta]$ and $x[\cdot]$ is an arbitrary quasimotion from the pencil $\mathcal{X}[t_0, x_0, U_i]$,*

$$X[\vartheta, t^*, x[t^*], U_i] \subset X[\vartheta, t_0, x_0, U_i].$$

Corollary 1. *Let U_i be a certain strategy from \mathfrak{A}_i and $x^*[\cdot] = x^*[\cdot, t_0, x_0, U_i]$ be some quasimotion of the system (2) from an initial position (t_0, x_0) that is induced by U_i . Consider $t^* \in [t_0, \vartheta]$ and let $x[t] = x[t, t^*, x^*[t^*], U_i]$, $t^* \leq t \leq \vartheta$ be an arbitrary quasimotion of the system (2) from the initial position $(t^*, x^*[t^*])$ that is induced by U_i . Then there exists a quasimotion $\tilde{x}[\cdot] \in \mathcal{X}[t_0, x_0, U_i]$ such that*

$$\tilde{x}[t] = \begin{cases} x^*[t] & \text{for } t_0 \leq t \leq t^*, \\ x[t] & \text{for } t^* \leq t \leq \vartheta. \end{cases}$$

Consequently, the quasimotion $x[t, t^*, x^*[t^*], U_i]$, $t^* \leq t \leq \vartheta$, is a segment of some quasimotion $\tilde{x}[\cdot]$ from the pencil $\mathcal{X}[t_0, x_0, U_i]$.

Counterexamples by Subbotin and Kononenko.

Malum consilium est, quod mutari potest.²

²Latin «It is a bad plan that admist of no modification.» This phrase is attributed to Publilius Syrus, (flourished 1st century BC), Latin mime writer contemporary with Cicero, chiefly remembered for a collection of versified aphorisms.

As we have mentioned earlier, Krasovskii's concept of motions of a dynamic system is extended to that of quasimotions in view of the two counterexamples suggested by Subbotin and Kononenko.

The first example demonstrates a possible occurrence of new motions [4] that were absent in the original pencil as the game evolved. This fact was first observed by Subbotin as follows.

Counterexample by Subbotin

We know the truth, not only by the reason, but also by the heart.
— Pascal³

Example 1. Let the controlled system (2) be given by

$$\dot{x} = u, \quad 0 \leq t \leq 2, \quad x[0] = x_0 = 0, \quad |v| \leq 1. \quad (9)$$

Consider the strategy

$$U \div u(t, x) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{при } x > 0, t \in [0, 1), \\ 0 & \text{при } x < 0, t \in [0, 1), \\ +1 & \text{при } x = 0, t \in [0, 1), \\ 0 & \text{при } x = 0, t \in [1, 2), \\ +1 & \text{при } x > 0, t \in [1, 2), \\ -1 & \text{при } x < 0, t \in [1, 2). \end{cases}$$

For this system, the pencil of all motions from the initial position $(t_0, x_0) = (0, 0)$ that are induced by the strategy U consists of the two elements, $x^{(1)}[t]$ and $x^{(2)}[t]$, $0 \leq t \leq 2$; see solid line in Figure 2. The same strategy U induces three motions from the initial position $(1, 0)$, namely, $x^{(1)}[t]$, $x^{(2)}[t]$, and $x^{(3)}[t] \equiv 0$, $1 \leq t \leq 2$. Thus, as the current position $(t, x[t])$ is shifting along the motion $x^{(1)}[t]$ or $x^{(2)}[t]$ at the time instant $t = 1$ the original pencil $\mathcal{X}[t_0, x_0, U]$ is augmented by the new motion $x^{(3)}[t]$, $1 \leq t \leq 2$, which was absent in $\mathcal{X}[t_0, x_0, U]$. Thus, as the game evolves, some segments of the original motions may be lost (see the next example by Kononenko) and new motions may also occur that were absent in the original pencil (the motion $x^{(3)}[t] \equiv 0$) in the current example).

The appearance of new motions (like $x^{(3)}[t] \equiv 0$, $1 \leq t \leq 2$) is undesired for the players choosing their own strategies. Indeed, a new motion yields new values of the decision criteria adopted by players. As a result, the optimal strategies of players in an initial position (the beginning of the game) may lose optimality as the game evolves if

³Blaise Pascal, (1623–1662), was a French mathematician, physician, religious figure, and writer.

Fig. 2. Pencil of motion from initial position (t_0, x_0)

a current position «reaches» the starting point of a new motion. This drawback can be eliminated with a slight modification of the concept of step-by-step motions [4]. More specifically, it is necessary to assume that the step-by-step motions may have finite jumps at partition points.

For instance, in the current example the motion $x[t] \equiv 0$, $0 \leq t \leq 2$, is the limit of the sequence of step-by-step quasimotions $x^{(k)}[t]$, $0 \leq t \leq 2$ ($k = 1, 2, \dots$): see dashed line in Figure 3. These quasimotions have finite jumps at the point $t = 1$ and are continuous at the other points of the interval $[0, 2]$.

Fig. 3. Step-by-step quasimotions and their limit

Here the convergence of $x^{(k)}[t]$ to $x[t] \equiv 0$ must be considered in the space $M_m[t_0, \vartheta]$ of all bounded n -dimensional functions with the norm $\|x(\cdot)\|_{M_m[t_0, \vartheta]} = \sup_{t_0 \leq t \leq \vartheta} \|x(t)\|$. With such a definition, the occurrence of new motions is eliminated and the players can make decisions (choose their strategies) without expecting new motions as the game evolves.

Counterexample by Kononenko

The next interesting counterexample was presented by Kononenko [2]. It demonstrates that a segment of a motion (in the sense of [4]) may cease to be a motion as the game evolves.

Example 2. Let the controlled system (2) be given by

$$\dot{x} = u, \quad 0 \leq t \leq 1, \quad x[0] = x_0 = 0, \quad |u| \leq 1.$$

Consider the strategy

$$U \div u(t, x) = \begin{cases} +1 & \text{при } x > 0, t \in [0, 1), \\ -1 & \text{при } x < 0, t \in [0, 1), \\ 0 & \text{при } x = 0, t \in [0, \frac{1}{2}) \cup (\frac{1}{2}, 1), \\ 1 & \text{при } x = 0, t = \frac{1}{2}. \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

A motion of this system from the initial position $(t_0, x_0) = (0, 0)$ that is induced by U is $x[t] \equiv 0, 0 \leq t \leq 1$; see bold line in Figure 4. However, its segment $x^{(3)}[t] \equiv 0, \frac{1}{2} \leq t \leq 1$, is not the motion on the interval $[\frac{1}{2}, 1]$ that starts from the position $(\frac{1}{2}, 0) = (\frac{1}{2}, x[\frac{1}{2}])$. On this interval, the motions are the straight-line segments $x^{(1)}[t] = t - \frac{1}{2}$ and $x^{(2)}[t] = -(t - \frac{1}{2}), t \in [\frac{1}{2}, 1]$, whereas the segment $x^3[t] \equiv 0, t \in [\frac{1}{2}, 1]$, is not a motion. Therefore, the segment $x[t] \equiv 0 (\frac{1}{2} \leq t \leq 1)$ is not the motion induced from the «current» initial position $(\frac{1}{2}, 0)$. This fact can be explained in the following way: the definition introduced in [4, p. 31] suggests no passage to the limit in the initial time instant, i.e., for a converging sequence of step-by-step motions only the initial positions $(t_0, x^{(k)})$ with a fixed time instant t_0 are considered.

In control problems and differential games, this fact may «deteriorate» an optimal strategy. Assume that, for a strategy adopted as the game solution, the performance criterion achieves optimum at the «end» of the motion and «its segment is lost» as the game evolves. Then, starting from some time instant (in Example 2, $t = \frac{1}{2}$), it is necessary to use another optimal strategy: the previous gives no result because the corresponding motion disappears. For avoiding such «a loss of segments», Kononenko suggested to define the step-by-step motions of system (2) with the passage to the limit in the initial time instant. That is, each step-by-step motion must be started from an initial position $(t^{(k)}, x^{(k)})$ instead of $(t_0, x^{(k)})$. Then such a step-by-step motion must be extended to the left to t_0 (if $t^{(k)} > t_0$). Due to Conditions 1, this extension is possible. For designing the motions $x[\cdot, t_0, x_0, U]$, the step-by-step motions $x(t, t^{(k)}, x^{(k)}, U, \Delta^{(k)})$, $t_0 \leq t \leq \vartheta$, that are extended to the left (if $t^{(k)} > t_0$) or truncated (if $t^{(k)} < t_0$) must be

Fig. 4. Lost segment of motion

considered in the limit sense under the constraint

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} |t^{(k)} - t_0| = 0. \quad (11)$$

For instance, the motion $x^{(3)}[t] \equiv 0$, $\frac{1}{2} \leq t \leq 1$ (see Figure 4) is the limit of the sequence of the step-by-step motions evolving from $(t^{(k)}, x^{(k)}) = (\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{10k}, 0)$, $k = 1, 2, \dots$

Consequently, the following result holds for the strategy (10).

Proposition [2]. Let $x[t] = x[t, t_0, x_0, U]$, $t_0 \leq t \leq \vartheta$, be the motion of the system (2) from an initial position (t_0, x_0) that is induced by the strategy U . Then, for any $t^* \in [t_0, \vartheta)$, the segment $x[t, t_0, x_0, U]$, $t^* \leq t \leq \vartheta$ is the motion of this system that is induced by U from the initial position $(t^*, x[t^*, t_0, x_0, U])$.

This explains the use of the limit (11) in the Definition of quasimotions.

5. TERMINAL PAYOFF FUNCTIONS

Consider again the NPDG (1) under Conditions 1 from section 2. Let each player i choose his positional strategy $U_i \in \mathfrak{A}_i$ ($i \in \mathbb{N}$) without making coalitions with other players. As a result, a strategy profile $U = (U_1, \dots, U_N) \in \mathfrak{A} = \prod_{i \in \mathbb{N}} \mathfrak{A}_i$ is formed. The strategy profile U induces a pencil $\mathcal{X}[t_0, x_0, U]$ of quasimotions from the initial position (t_0, x_0) . The intersection of this pencil with the hyperplane $t = \vartheta$ is a compact subset — the attainability domain $X[\vartheta, t_0, x_0, U \div Q] = X[\vartheta]$ (see Proposition 3). The payoff function of each player $i \in N$, $\mathcal{J}_i = F_i(x[\vartheta])$, is defined on $X[\vartheta]$. The value of this function is adopted for assessing the performance of player i in the game (1) and called his payoff. Without special mention, accept

Conditions 2. In the game (1), the scalar functions $F_i(x)$ ($i \in \mathbb{N}$) are continuous in the space \mathbb{R}^m .

In the theory of differential games, the payoff functions of the form $\mathcal{J}_i = F_i(x[\vartheta])$ are said to be terminal because they are defined at the «right limits» ($t = \vartheta$) of the quasimotions $x[\cdot] = x[t, t_0, x_0, U]$, $t_0 \leq t \leq \vartheta$.

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